

ARCHITECTURE

THE FUTURE OF OLD INDUSTRIES: DEVELOPMENT CONCEPT FOR ABSHERON

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Abstract

At the turn of the XX-XXI centuries in connection with the transition to market relations the city authorities of Baku and Sumgait faced with the challenge of ageing and dilapidation of industrial zones. As a result, large in Absheron areas in the central part of these cities remain closed and not integrated into the urban environment. This problem against the background of the acute shortage of land in Absheron Peninsula is quite urgent and requires immediate intervention by the relevant organizations.

The article focused on development of the rehabilitation concept of industrial zones on Absheron peninsula for their integration into the urban structure. The research methodology is based on a systematic approach, which includes the analysis of literary and archive materials, collection and analysis of master plans and urban planning documents of cities and settlements in Absheron, studying of experience in the renovation of old industrial zones and the adaptive reuse of industrial facilities, analysis of National Urban Planning Regulations, Strategic Road map for the National Economy of Azerbaijan (SRMNEA) and Greater Baku Regional Development Plan (GBRDP), classification of industrial zones in Absheron by investment potential, and development of the rehabilitation concept of industrial zones in Absheron peninsula.

The article will highlight some of the key results of recent studies that show the modern experience of the renovation of old industrial zones in urban structure and the adaptive reuse of industrial facilities. As a result of the study, the directions and main approaches to the rehabilitation of former industrial zones in Absheron were identified, the sequence of works on rehabilitation and renovation of these zones was revealed, the basic principles of industrial areas renovation were developed and the methods of reconstruction and adaptive use of industrial facilities of Baku and Sumgait were determined. The paper also proposes the methodological basis of the author's approach to the renovation of industrial zones in Absheron and shows how 4 different models of rehabilitation of industrial zones are offered in different situations. The proposed models and results of the study can be used in the rehabilitation and renovation of industrial zones of Baku and Sumgait, as well as other cities of Azerbaijan

Keywords: old industries, development concept, Absheron peninsula, Baku and Sumgait, adaptive reuse, renovation, industrial heritage

1. INTRODUCTION

At various stages of their history, society makes new demands on environment, including industrial areas located in urban areas. The formation of Baku industrial zones occurred at the late XIX – the early XX centuries, when resulting from the oil boom Baku in a short time turned from a small settlement inside the fortress into the largest industrial regional center (Fatullayev-Figarov). The industrial zones of Sumgait-city which located in the North-Western part of Absheron refers to a later period (1932), when the city was originally built as an alternative to Baku (satellite town) to ease in overcrowding functions of the capital-city (Mamedbeyov). The oil and petrochemical industry continues to play a crucial role in the further stages of the historical development of Absheron cities and settlements (Nagiyev). Thus, the natural historically formed oil production conditions determined the scattered settlement system in Absheron Peninsula with the core in Baku and satellites in workers' settlements around it and contributed to the allocation of industrial and residential zones here. They also determined the formation of a three-part development pattern of Baku

with an industrial zone in the middle and residential areas in the West and East (Gahramanova, 2012).

After the collapse of the USSR the transition to a market economy and the change of economic development track led to a significant depreciation of industrial facilities and the emergence of contradictions between the existing urban environment and the new needs of society. Today, many industrial buildings of Absheron having lost their original function are isolated from the urban environment. Regeneration of industrial zones and adaptation of old industrial buildings to new conditions is very important. Some of these buildings are monuments of industrial heritage of Baku and Absheron and evidence of their historical development. In addition, "ageing" of industrial buildings, both physical and moral, creates a number of problems [Yakovlev, 2014]. Among them a high level of environmental pollution, traffic congestion, inability to use these areas in urban development are sources of particular concern. This has been the challenges faced by many former industrial cities [Usoltseva, 2015; Sinitsyna, 2005].

Thus, the problem of rehabilitation of former industrial complexes, their integration in urban context and adaptation to new urban processes is quite acute in

Baku and all Absheron Peninsula and determines the relevance of this study. As a result of de-industrialization, significant areas will be released for urban infrastructure, housing, improvement of the transport system. Former industrial areas with buildings, production facilities and transport infrastructure occupy the large area in the center of Baku, which makes it extremely attractive for investors.

As can be seen from international and domestic best practice for rehabilitation of former industrial zones, new requirements for production and the surrounding area could not be resolved in an add-on manner of new elements [Starkova, 2015; Kotenko, 2015]. There is a need for qualitative transformation and regeneration of former industrial areas, which is an important condition for solving strategic tasks of urban development. Bearing in mind that until recently matters relating to renovation of industrial zones and adaptive use of industrial facilities of Absheron had been neglected the tasks of reconstruction and renovation of industrial zones in Absheron need theoretical support for analytical research in this field. In this regard we should note a number of works devoted to the transformation of urban environment and architectural image of industrial complexes in big cities (Belousov, V. N., Blokhin, V. V., Kim N. N., Korepina T. N., Kulaga V. A., Bocharov Yu. P., etc.). In these works attention was paid to renovation of out-of-date buildings and blocks and reconstruction of industrial facilities. However, these works do not meet the realities of today, when entire zones needed to be transformed, bearing in mind the social, economic and environmental consequences of these transformations.

Later, in 1980s and 1990s various approaches and reconstruction methods of industrial complexes, bearing in mind the architectural-planning factor and environmental approach have also been addressed in the works of (Bakhtin N., Dolgova, O. V., Drogana, Sinitsa, etc.). However, these proposals have seldom been implemented.

World experience in industrial facilities reuse and methods of changing the function in former manufactures are presented in these works of (Maciej Klopotoski and Marek Zagroba; Alfrey, J., & Putnam, T.; Banham, R.; Bluestone, B., & Harrison, B.; Bullen, P. A., & Love, P. E. D.; Bullen, P. A., & Love, P. E. D.; Chen, J., Judd, B., & Hawken, S.; Langston, C., Wong, F. K. W., Hui, E. C. M., & Shen, L.; Bie Plevoets & K. Van Cleempoel.; Cities under Socialism: and After?; Emscher Park: from dereliction to scenic landscapes.; Hirt, S. Post-socialist urban forms: notes from Sofia; Hirt, S. Whatever happened to the (post)socialist city?)

Some latest works which have examined directly the problems of regeneration and rehabilitation of former industrial zones as well as the adaptive reuse of industrial buildings stand out (Bystrov, Bystrova T. Y., Demidova E. V., Karmatskaya A. A., Kotenko I. A., Safonov D. E., Silogaeva B. W., Sinitsyna N. N., Starkova N. In. Timchenko R. A., Usoltseva M. S., Chayko A. A., Yakovlev A. A., Bakhtina, Drogan, etc.).

METODOLOGY

The method consists of theoretical assumption and methods of investigation. Methodology involves theoretical issues that guide the directions of collecting and analyzing literature/data/information on state and rehabilitation ways of industrial areas in cities.

It includes:

- analysis of key findings in recent researches, which show how urban planning, economic, social and aesthetical/psychological aspects are connected to rehabilitation of industrial zones of cities and settlement in Absheron and their integration into urban context;

- collecting and analyzing master plans and urban development documents of cities and settlements of Absheron (Baku, Sumgait, Khirdalan etc.), consultations with Baku State Design Institute, Azerbaijan State Design institute and Azerbaijan Industrial Design Institute to perceive the structure and dynamics of industrial zones in urban structure;

- studying relevant literature (articles, books), which represent an experience in renovation of industrial zones and adaptive reuse of former industrial objects in international and domestic practice;

- analysis of SRMNEA and GBRDP.

2. Backgrounds of renovation and rehabilitation of former industrial areas in Absheron

Analysis of recent research findings, official statistical data, as well as data on industrial zones conditions and their infrastructure collected from the design institutes shows that the feasibility of renovation of industrial zones in Baku and Absheron arises from the following factors:

3.1. Economic background. Under current conditions in Azerbaijan there is an extreme unevenness in spatial distribution of productive forces. Over the past two decades, the settlement system has been developing archaic. Only two major cities (Ganja and Sumgait) and one metropolis (Baku) are located in the country. Baku (about 4 million people) and Sumgait (320 thousand people) located in Absheron Peninsula attract investments and labor resources from all over Azerbaijan. First of all, this is the economic burden that the region carries on a national scale. Greater Baku accounts for 77% of the volume of total production. The population concentrated in the area of 6% (Absheron) of the total area of Azerbaijan is equal 36% of the total country population. Such disparities clearly demonstrate both the weight of Absheron region and the challenges facing Azerbaijan in a given situation. Due to poor state of transport communication between cities and settlements (high-speed railway transport, ramified highways network, etc.), there are practically no sustainable social and economic linkages between regions, the mobility of the population is minimized. There are no highly efficient industrial clusters in the country, the infrastructure was outdated. The fact that a large part of the machinery and equipment is obsolescent and worn out is making working condition worse. After the collapse of the USSR, Absheron's industrial clusters have not yet fully restored the integrity of their structure due to the emergence of bankrupt and inactive plants and factories.

At the same time, like many countries of the post-Soviet space, urbanization in Azerbaijan had moved from the phase of socialist (government) to that of capitalist, where the economic and social interests of people prevail over the urban planning ones. State capital investment in the territorial development was replaced by private sector investments, which are subordinated to market laws and is designed to make a quick profit [Demidova, 2013]. That is why an important objective for a government at this stage is to improve the national tax policy to raise an interest of developers in investing in former industrial zones rehabilitation, creation of new industrial parks both in Absheron and in the whole country.

3.2. Urban planning background. Industrial areas cover about 30% of Baku-city area and 65% of Sumgait-city area (fig.1). Closure of many industries, reduction of volumes of manufactures makes many town-planning problems worse in the territory of Absheron settlements, including efficiency in the land use, creation of comfortable living environment, improvement of planning and functional decisions, spatial composition of the cities, development of transport infrastructure, etc. In planning structure of Greater Baku with a large number of industrial enterprises it is difficult to find free lands for new construction in already developed districts. Analysis of the land structure in Absheron Peninsula suggests that there is a huge shortage of land there. In such a state of emergency, rehabilitation of former industrial areas is very relevant for urban development needs in Baku and Absheron [Gahramanova, Babayev, 2017].

A modern city is inconceivable without a developed safe and comfortable public space. Nowadays the urban pattern of Baku responded only partially to these needs. It is characterized by low-quality housing and deficiency in recreational areas, a high percentage of industrial and warehouse areas in the city center, an unfavorable transport situation (the level of infrastructure development does not correspond to traffic load). Thus, rehabilitation of derelict areas of Baku with dilapidated buildings and a shortage of land for new construction is a way out of this situation.

3.3. Social background. Urban planning structure of Baku, in all its compactness, is mixed, aggressive and chaotic. The comprehensive regeneration of inner-city industrial sites in Baku and Sumgait, which are often adjacent to residential blocks, will lead to humanizing the urban environment, increasing its social and architectural value, saturation of the environment with variety of functions (public, residential, industrial), creation of new public and business spaces (museums, galleries, clubs, loft apartments, etc.). This is also facilitated by the fact that industrial buildings have a huge

architectural potential, in particular, they have non-standard spaces, huge areas, original constructive solutions, etc.

Due to development of innovations and advanced technologies, industrial cities are transformed into administrative and business centers [Timchenko, 2010]. Former industrial zones are replaced by modern buildings [Chaiko, 2007; Karmatskaya, 2012]. Nowadays most of industrial facilities in Baku are "outside" the urban environment. Thus, it has become necessary to rehabilitate the industrial zones in the city and adapt them to modern-day circumstances.

3.4. Environmental background. Currently, the issues of regeneration of outdated industrial complexes are on the agenda in Baku and Absheron. Many of them do not meet environmental standards. In addition, the concentration of large oil refineries, engineering and energy enterprises polluting the air and water basins, soils and landscapes of Absheron, largely affects the well-being of people [Gahramanova, 2012]. 16 thousand hectares of land are polluted by oil and petroleum products, 2196 hectares are contaminated by chemical waste in Absheron peninsula. About half of the area of Baku and Sumgait is high dangerous pollution.

Reducing industries in Baku (especially heavy or manufacturing industry) and reclamation of the territories will improve the environmental situation in the region. For meaningful changes in rehabilitation of industrial zones, the financial and legislative assistance of the government is necessary [Usoltseva M. S., 2015; Safonova, 2012].

3.5. Aesthetic and psychological background. Every resident of the city has a natural need to live in a fully-fledged architectural and landscape environment. Diverse aesthetic environment impacts his or her psychological well-being. In particular, visual, sound, cultural, socio-ecological and socio-psychological aspects of this influence hold great meaning [Tetior, 2009; Safonova, 2012]. Unfortunately, contemporary urban environment of Baku and Sumgait does not meet the requirements of residents and has a negative impact on their psychological state. This fact was noted by residents of the nearby areas of Baku and Sumgait in their interviews and statements. Most of the abandoned industrial buildings in Absheron are architecturally inexpressive, the production areas look depressing. As a consequence, there is a need to conduct a complex of works upon improvement the interior and appearance of industrial buildings in harmony with current requirements (to bring them in line with the surrounding buildings, local cultural and national traditions, etc.) [Bystrov, 2006].

Figure 1. Industrial zones in Absheron

3. Determination of development ways of post-industrial zones in Absheron

Rehabilitation of each individual territory is unique and unrepeatable. Methods of rehabilitation of former industrial zones are based on the uniqueness of the place and depend on many factors, such as economic, social, natural landscape, etc. In addition to urban planning issues the process of rehabilitation of urban industrial estates includes also technical, organizational, legal, economic, etc. activities.

Our General strategy for the rehabilitation of industrial zones in Absheron is directed toward sustainable urban development, in which all components of urban environment (manufacture, infrastructure, management, human resources, environment, etc.) underwent change at the same time. However, the choice of the

strategy depends on many factors, including the presence of industrial heritage in the site (Demidova, 2013, p.10).

The rehabilitation of the former industrial areas in Absheron can be defined as the organizational transformation of the fabric of industrial zones in the following areas: **technical re-equipment, social development, economic recovery and environmental rehabilitation** (Fig.2). The technical re-equipment means the replacement and technical improvement of existing facilities. Social development in this case is designed to strengthen social activity in the transformed urban space. As for the economic recovery, we are talking about the economic profitability of new functions of the enterprises in a market economy. Environmental rehabilitation of post-industrial areas is directed toward improvement of economic situation, creating conditions for sustainable development of the rehabilitated area.

Figure 2. The main objectives of the former industrial areas rehabilitation in Absheron

Analysis of the state of industrial areas in Absheron (Baku, Sumgait, Khirdalan and villages) reveals that all three approaches to their renovation, which are used in modern practice of industrial zones transformation, may be used at rehabilitation of these areas (Fig.3):

1) **Complete removal** of industrial facilities and **re-functionalization** of the post-industrial area (the coastal industrial zone and former “Black city” area in Baku). Three trends can be defined in full re-functionalization of these areas – **restructuring** of existing industrial buildings, **environmental rehabilitation** of former industrial areas and **total demolition** of industrial enterprises and **redevelopment** of abandoned industrial sites.

During the re-functionalization of former industrial facilities the urban environment is filling up with new functions that are more relevant and in demand at

present. It may be housing, administrative, business, educational, cultural, commercial, sports, recreational and mixed functions. Ecological rehabilitation of industrial areas is being undertaken with the view to create green spaces (parks, public gardens, etc.) on reclaimed areas (Starkova, 2015). This approach was partly under application in the western side of coastal industrial area, where the renovation has led to extension of Baku Boulevard. The State Flag square, shopping centers are situated here now. The refitting work was done at the Baku shipyard named after Paris Commune and there is a “XX-XXI Century Azerbaijani painting” Museum here. Former Hydroelectric Power Station named after Krasin was turned into Museum of Stone Relics, a warehouse for Caspian flotilla warships was transformed into YARAT Contemporary Art Space.

Figure 3. Basic approaches to rehabilitation of industrial zones of Absheron

However, full demolition of industrial facilities and land redevelopment are most frequent in practice of rehabilitation of old industrial zones. It's normally used if the spatial and functional organization of industrial estates doesn't match the urban value and potential of the area. In particular, such lands in Baku are used to create new housing. Thus, a project of "Baku White city" had been proposed and was being developed in the territory of the former "Black city" (221 hectares), which is located in one part of the former industrial estate of Baku. The new housing estate was designed for 50 thousand inhabitants (a joint project of architecture firms "Atkins", "Fosters + Partners", and "F+A Architects") [Bagirova-Ibrahimli, 2017]. It is proposed to place 10 new residential districts there. Among all of the positive outcomes of the project, the main concept of which is architectural variety, environmental compatibility and careful integration of new construction into the urban context, however, there is one regarding which we feel compelled to note a concern for possible future trends. It is doubtful, how could they, with in the short period, have reclaimed so large area, in which oil production and processing continued for over a century.

Reuse of former industrial estates gives the possibility to develop the lands according to the modern principles of spatial planning. This approach usually provides extensive territorial planning, involving not only the vacated area, but also the surrounding buildings. All this requires the mandatory participation of government authorities in this type of redevelopment projects. In this case the majority of industrial enterprises that have lost their profitability are taken out of the outskirts of the city. Thus, in the case of Baku, the Greater Baku Regional Development Plan provides relocation of many industries from the city center to Alat,

which will reduce environmental stress in towns and cities in Absheron.

2) Partial removal of industrial facilities and re-functionalization of the industrial estates (former industrial zone of Baku, partly coastal industrial zone). Three important of such measures will be mentioned - **reconstruction** and **preservation** of the urban structure with identifying and recognizing patterns of stability; **museumification (conservation)** of industrial heritage; **integration the new building** seamlessly into historical environment. During the reconstruction and preservation of the planning structure, the re-equipment or partial reduction of old industrial complexes are usually produced. The methods of filling the old industrial areas with new functions by adding new buildings to existing ones can be applied. This technique is useful for the central industrial zone of Baku. Former warehouse and industrial facilities might find a new use in re-functionalization process (Universal Machine Building, Plant of domestic refrigerators "Chinar", CroPlast Pipe plant, Eurodesign Warehouse, etc.). The urban planning methods of reconstruction are narrower here than in the case removal of industrial facilities. However, the presence of these industrial facilities may be a starting point for economic recovery (establishments of industrial parks, etc.).

In the case of presence of industrial heritage like coastal zone of Baku, the territory is perceived as a historical environment with its own composition and planning structure. Old ship repair plants or oil industries located here, for example SAGA Ship Repair Company, SOCAR Oil and Gas Construction trust, etc. can be filled with other functions. But the "spirit of place" should be preserved owing to the unique historical environment, which is very important for creating a place brand.

The financial side of the issue was of considerable significance in the renovation and rehabilitation of the former industrial zones in Absheron. However, the above mentioned method allows us to use existing facilities with little investment and preserve the industrial heritage. Thus, there are many examples of creating interesting and sustainable structures inside of former plants, such as local creative clusters that attract young people and require large spaces (workshops, art studios, galleries, etc.). These clusters may eventually become a stable planning unit capable of boosting economic growth of the area (Starkova, 2015)

3) Preservation of industrial function of the old industrial estates (industrial area of Sumgait-city). Here, the two trends are visible - *memorial way*, where the complete restoration of the building with respect pay to the original design is done (in the case of industrial heritage) and *reconstructive way*, when the implementation of new technologies in the body of existing building and reconstruction of plants and warehouses is produced (Fig.4.). This way implies the preservation of industrial functions in the light of advanced in technology and modernization of production lines, capacity, and cleaner production system. It also means reducing the space of industries and their sanitary zones, consolidation industries (industrial parks). Attention should also be given to creating a comfortable production environment. The reconstructive way is most suitable to the industrial zone of Sumgait-city. This industrial estate was created in 1930s and was one of the largest ones in Azerbaijan and in the USSR (Mammadbayov).

It was also a source of severe pollution of landscapes and high mortality rates among the city population in 1980s (Nagiyev).

In fact, the deterioration of the old infrastructure in industrial estates provides a chance to improve the ecology of the region and to create sustainable industrial clusters on the basis of existing plants. It will also facilitate the economic recovery of the region. The work on creation of Industrial park in Sumgait (Sumgait Technologies Park) began since 2009. This industrial park includes the plants of heavy engineering, precision machining and pressing of industrial gases, polymer products, metal smelting, cable plant, engineering plant, solar panels, production of sandwich panels etc. However, production volumes are small. Thus, in 1980-1985 in the territory of Sumgait the lands aside for industries accounted for over 2000,0 hectares, and the number of employed reached 50,0 thousand people. Majority of the employed fell mainly into plants of heavy industry. The share of local light industries was negligible. Despite the fact that in 2018 the city population increased by more than 50% in comparison with that period, people working in industry scarcely reached 20,0 thousand people and only half of them employed in heavy industry. The remaining 10,0 thousand people work in the newly established enterprises of light industry located in small-size areas [Bakı şəhərinin planlaşdırma layihəsi. İzahat hissəsi "Azərdövlətlayihə". DBLI, Bakı, 2011]

Figure 4. Industrial estates of Sumgait-city - subject to rehabilitation

5. Priorities for works on rehabilitation of Absheron industrial zones

To identify the methods of renovation and rehabilitation of industrial estates in Absheron the priorities for work to be carried out at different levels should be identified (Fig.5):

Figure 5. Phasing on rehabilitation of Absheron industrial zones

1. **Area planning** focused on identifying current urban challenges in the industrial areas of Baku and Sumgait at the macro level (the most problematic cities in Absheron). The analysis of social and transport infrastructure, built environment, population structure and standard-related issues are carried out here. The priority for works on rehabilitation of Absheron industrial zones is assessed on the basis of various factors (economic, social, environmental, urban planning, innovation, operational, technological, engineering, etc.) with a view to identifying the most effective methods of renovation in each particular case.

2. **Harmonization** with GBRDP and the SRMNEA. It is necessary to identify a package of measures that will contribute to the transformation of the industrial estates in Baku and Absheron and meet the goals and objectives of the city and settlement development in Absheron. Undertaking wide-ranging questionnaire surveys of citizens, interviews with experts in the field of urban planning, economics, etc., public hearings and discussions of all interested parties, special studies will help to identify the micro-level objectives, as well as the needs of the population and people on business.

3. **Choice of methods** for renovation and rehabilitation. It makes the analysis of the main tasks on territory renovation covering various urban levels. Study and adjustment of land use rules in the territory of the industrial zone, which will then provide the basis to change the functional zoning and create the renovation project in Absheron cities.

6. Classification of industrial areas in Absheron Peninsula according to investment appeal

On the basis of the author's analysis of the master plans of Absheron's cities and settlements (Baku, Sumgait etc.), SRMNEA, GBRDP and field studies, the industrial areas of Absheron are classified according to investment appeal. In accordance with this classification, the industrial zones of Absheron are divided into the following groups (Fig.6.):

- Investment-attractive zones in terms of restoring the production. This group includes the industrial zone of Sumgait-city. The analysis revealed a satisfactory condition of building structures, "tolerable" land contamination, developed engineering and transport infrastructure. To restore industrial functions, it is necessary to modernize production lines, improve industrial facilities with a view to transforming them into compact and environmentally friendly clusters and creating a comfortable working environment here.

- Investment-attractive zones in order to change production functions. This group includes industrial zones in the central or coastal part of Baku. The analysis revealed mainly satisfactory condition of building structures, permissible land contamination, developed engineering and transport infrastructure. It is proposed to carry out work on the partial reduction of former industrial complexes, fill of industrial areas with new functions, create local creative clusters (workshops, studios, galleries, etc.) here.

- Low investment-attractive zones, which proposes a change in functions. These zones are located in the peripheral areas of Baku-city. As a rule, these are

the territories of former oil wells. The analysis revealed mainly unsatisfactory condition of building structures, high land contamination, poorly developed engineering and transport infrastructure. It is offered partial and/or complete demolition of abandoned

buildings and filling with (or chancing in) new functions such as housing, administrative and office, education, cultural and entertainment, trade, sports, recreation and mixed use, etc. Preliminary land reclamation is needed.

CLASSIFICATION OF INDUSTRIAL AREAS ON ABSHERON ACCORDING TO INVESTMENT APPEAL			
INVESTMENT APPEAL	SUGGESTED FUNCTION	LOCATION	VIEW
<p>INVESTMENT-ATTRACTIVE</p> <p>The analysis revealed a satisfactory condition of building structures, "tolerable" land contamination, developed engineering and transport infrastructure</p>	<p>INDUSTRIAL FUNCTION</p> <p>modernization of production lines, improvement of industrial facilities with a view to transforming them into compact and environmentally friendly clusters and creating a comfortable working space</p>	<p>INDUSTRIAL ZONE OF SUMGAIT</p>	
<p>INVESTMENT-ATTRACTIVE</p> <p>The analysis revealed mainly satisfactory condition of building structures, permissible land contamination, developed engineering and transport infrastructure.</p>	<p>CHANGE IN PRODUCTION FUNCTION</p> <p>partial reduction of former industrial complexes, fill of industrial area environment with new functions, create local creative clusters (workshops, studios, galleries)</p>	<p>COASTAL AND NORTHERN INDUSTRIAL ZONE OF BAKU</p>	
<p>LOW INVESTMENT-ATTRACTIVE</p> <p>The analysis revealed mainly unsatisfactory condition of building structures, high land contamination, poorly developed engineering and transport infrastructure.</p>	<p>CHANGE IN PRODUCTION FUNCTION</p> <p>partial and/or complete demolition of abandoned buildings and filling and/or replacement with new functions such as housing, administrative and office, education, cultural and entertainment, trade, sports, recreation and mixed use.</p>	<p>FORMER OIL WELLS OF BAKU</p>	

Figure 6. Classification of industrial areas in Absheron Peninsula according to investment appeal

7. Basic principles of renovation of industrial zones in Absheron

Based on the findings of an analysis of industrial zones facilities, as well as the review of the literature and projects concerning the global experience of industrial zones renovation and adaptive use of old industrial facilities, following suggestions on *basic principles of renovation* were made (Fig.7), which are used then in development of rehabilitation concept and basic renovation models of industrial zones in Baku and Sumgait:

- **The principle of comprehensiveness and consistency of renovation**, which includes activities designed to create the new functions and planning structure in industrial areas alongside the interests of the city as a whole. The landscapes of Absheron, including the territories of the former industrial zones, are seen as a balanced and interrelated environmental system, where changes in any of its subsystems lead to the change of the other ones.

- **The principle of the rating value** where the analysis and classification of Absheron industrial territories according to investment appeal are carried out.

- **The principle of inventory** which identifies the elements of the planning structure and built environment of industrial zones, as well as the presence of architectural and historical heritage and assessment of their value in the spatial structure of the city.

- **The principle of priority** which determines the priority of Absheron industrial areas renovation from an economic and environmental point of view.

- **The principle of algorithmicity** which determines the sequence of renovation works.

- **The principle of ecological continuity** in Absheron industrial zones that would involve creating an environmentally favorable climate, both in the industrial zone and in the surrounding areas by switching to environmentally friendly and knowledge-based industries, removing harmful industries, etc.

- **The principle of adaptation** makes it possible to change the functions of industrial areas after redevelopment (multifunctional centers, museums, creative clusters, housing, etc.).

- **The principle of humanization** involves the restructuring of former industrial areas for the needs of the public and the creation of a more humane urban environment with new green spaces, essential services, sports and recreation.

- **The principle of social trust**, which the main goal is to create a comfortable urban environment for various population categories, including groups with special needs.

- **The principle of the cultural matrix** based on religion and local tradition, national context, which are the core for identification and self-identification of urban space.

- **The principle of bio-positivity** which is expressed in the maximum greening both area of former industrial area subject to renovation and Absheron peninsula as a whole (vertical gardening, green roofs construction, etc.), rehabilitation of abandoned areas that will support the creation of urban spaces close to natural environment.

- **The principle of polyfunctionality** expressed in the creation of a multifunctional urban environment

which elements are organized simultaneously "layered" on top over time.

- **The principle of multilevel approach** where pedestrian and traffic movement, as well as areas with different functions are separated vertically at different levels (vertical zoning).

- **The principle of good communication** determined by the possibility of free movement and visual overview of the urban environment.

- **The principle of environmental accessibility** expressed by the possibility of providing people with easy access to urban environment without transport communications, natural barriers, etc.

Figure 7. Basic principles of renovation of industrial zones in Absheron

8. Methods of reconstruction and adaptive use of industrial facilities in Absheron

I would like to highlight the main methods of reconstruction or adaptive use of industrial facilities that might be used to adapt the old industrial architecture of Baku and Absheron to our times (Fig.8):

- **the method of "applique"** in which the aim is to create a composition on the bases of existing building structure (for example, surface reconstruction of building facades, construction of "false facade" covering, i.e. the forming volumetric composition form varying in texture and colour forms). Thus, a beautiful shell that often regardless of building structure is created.

- **the method of "analogies"** focused on comparing the designed industrial building with figurative analogues (in the case of industrial architecture it may be, for instance, functional or technical analogies) in order to give it new qualities. Examples of such techniques can be the placement of engineering equipment on the building facade, symbolic display of the technological cycle or production on the building facade, etc.

- **the method of "integration"**, that implies the integration of new elements and structures into the existing building design. As an example, the methods of creating new or increasing the expressiveness of the former dominants, the extension of buildings, changing the scale of buildings (adaptation to the surrounding buildings by height, style, etc.) may be cited.

Figure 8. Basic methods of reconstruction or adaptive use of industrial facilities in Absheron

Thus, the discussed above current directions, methods and techniques of industrial areas rehabilitation in Absheron and adaptation of old industrial buildings to our times are based on the adaptation of industrial heritage to innovative technologies and reconstruction of "inefficient" industries, changing their functions. These methods and techniques will help the old industrial facilities to adapt to the urban structure of rapidly developing cities and settlements of Absheron.

9. Methodological framework of the author's approach to the concept development of industrial areas in Absheron

In conceptualizing of Absheron's industrial zones rehabilitation I have been guided by the following considerations. The transformation of the industrial areas in Absheron will have two directions: internal and external. The external course is based on the needs of the city and full-fledged vital activities of the population. Inside, first of all, it is necessary to provide a sustainable environment, in economic, environmental and social point of view.

These two directions promote us to solve the problems of dynamic balance in the transformation of old industrial areas. These issues were conducted in the

school of Management at the University of Massachusetts in the middle of the 20th century, where methods of "industrial dynamics" were developed. They have achieved good results in their studies, bearing in mind the dynamic behavior of systems and changing the individual structural units of the system

Thus, the author formulated the development concept of industrial zones in Absheron which is expressed in the creation of environmentally sustainable and people-centered, economically self-sufficient and active in innovative urban spaces.

I would like to propose using the cluster approach in the rehabilitation of industrial areas in Absheron, which provides more diverse perspectives in development of selective industrial areas. This is facilitated by the fact that each cluster is a multifunctional self-sufficient sustainable structural unit.

For the first time the concept of cluster was introduced by Michael Porter in his "On Competition", where he defines it as concentration of interconnected businesses (suppliers, manufactures, etc.) and associated institutions (educational, infrastructure and administrative) in a particular field (Porter, 1998). In fact, Porter continued Alfred Marshall's studies who

worked to determine the reliance of success in the economic sector on placement of specialized industries (Samostrelva, 2012, Bystrova T. Yu. Analysis of methods of rehabilitation of industrial urban areas).

In our case, we can present the proposed clusters as open self-sufficient and sustainable interlinked (by horizontal ties) groups of units and expand the range of their functions (it may be industrial, creative, public, etc.). Sustainability of groups is understood as economic, environmental, social and innovative resilience of groups. The "renewed" industrial clusters of Absheron should be simultaneously focused on the harmonious integration into the socio-cultural urban environment, as well as have the ability to self-recovery and reproduction of the environment. In addition to output goods the "final product" of the renewed clusters will be social ties and a sustainable natural environment, which will be greatly facilitated by innovation.

The creation of clusters (industrial, creative, public, etc.) in the old industrial areas of Absheron is aimed at:

- justification of external relations of the renovated territory on the basis of urban planning, historical and socio-cultural studies of needs, traditions and life-style

of the population, which will express the urban environment uniqueness;

- determination of quantitative and qualitative parameters of the state and development prospects of the natural landscapes on the territory of old industries (assessment of natural components, comprehensive architectural and landscape analysis, natural and climatic assessment of the territory);

- definition of the strategic goal of the renovation project of industrial areas in close connection with the urban-natural component, taking into account the possibility of natural landscapes restoration.

- arrangement of multi-level and multi-element urban environment on the rehabilitated area of Absheron as an open system of clusters, where one of the goals is to achieve a balance between internal and external systems.

- determination of the full economic impact of the rehabilitation and activities related to the unlocking the urban potential of industrial zones.

The study offers 4 basic rehabilitation models of industrial zones in Absheron on the basis of structural and morphological analysis of the investigated areas (Fig.9):

REHABILITATION MODEL OF INDUSTRIAL AREAS ON ABSHERON			
MODEL	OBJECT OF REGENERATION	ARCHITECTURAL ENSEMBLE	FUNCTION
«FRAGMENTARY» MODEL		MIX-USED URBAN ENVIRONMENT	
«LINEAR-NODULAR» MODEL		CULTURAL AND RECREATION SPACE	
«COMPLEX» MODEL		CULTURAL, BUSINESS, HOUSING, COMMERCIAL AND SERVICE SPACE	
«EVOLUTIONARY REVIVAL» MODEL		RENOVATED INDUSTRIAL CLUSTERS	

Figure 9. Rehabilitation models of the industrial zones in Absheron

- "fragmentary" model - open landscaped space, which function can be a mixed-use urban environment. This may include creative clusters, art objects, seasonal exhibitions, museums, areas for folk festivals, etc. As a rule, commercial and cultural services become an integral part of such clusters. Enriching the environment occurs through creation of architectural objects and small architectural forms, by means of horizontal and vertical greening, decoration of facades with graffiti, etc. Such solution is proposed for the historical industrial zone of Baku with developed infrastructure, which

has lost their function due to developing technology. Rehabilitation of the former industrial areas should be provided through refunctionalizing of industrial facilities.

- "linear-nodular" model - spaces created by a set of local nodules (multifunctional objects) located along a specified trajectory (line). After renovation such objects can be used for cultural events (theaters, museums, exhibitions, concert halls, etc.). Single building or group of buildings, as well as elements of recreational and sports activities which are landmarks in the urban

environment serve as nodules in this model. This model can be used in the coastal industrial zone of Baku and can serve as a transition zone between the functionally enriched central zone and the Boulevard zone of Baku. Due to the sufficient length of the Baku Boulevard, it is necessary to increase the number of "attraction points».

- "*complex*" model is the largest renovation project in scale, where the goal is to create a multifunctional environment with a predominance of cultural, business, housing, commercial and service functions and well-developed infrastructure (self-sufficient district). Proposed locations are the peripheral industrial zones in Baku. According to this model, "White city" renovation project was proposed on the territory of "Black city" in Baku.

- "*evolutionary revival*" model, in which the old industrial areas of Absheron with high industrial development potential are transformed into new areas without change in function but bearing in mind the principles of sustainable development. Here, old industries are restored in a new format – the format of "renovated" industrial clusters. It is necessary to revise some production cycles, the profitability of which is dubious in the new market relations. Bearing in mind the development of innovative technologies and the trend of shift toward knowledge-based industries, as well as the improvement of urban environment and working conditions this model proposes to reconstruct and modernize industrial complexes by switching to environmentally friendly, "open" industries, maximum landscaping, etc. This model can be successfully applied in the industrial zone of Sumgait-city, where creating a Sumgait Technological Park on the basis of redevelopment of old industrial enterprises has already begun.

DISCUSSIONS

In reviewing the study it was revealed that although a common set of principles for the renovation were offered to develop the rehabilitation concept of industrial areas in Absheron, some of them played an ambiguous role in the specific areas of Absheron Peninsula (coastal industrial zone and central industrial zone of Baku, industrial zone of Sumgait-city, etc.). Thus, if the principles of comprehensiveness and consistency, rating value, inventory, priority, algorithmicity, ecological continuity, bio-positivity and environmental accessibility are acceptable to all industrial zones of Absheron, while the principles of adaptation, humanization, social trust, polyfunctionality, multilevel approach and good communication are more suited for industrial zones, which will change their function in a future. We need to take special note of the principle of cultural matrix, which determines the identity and artistic and aesthetic quality of the environment.

The proposed two directions of industrial zones rehabilitation in Absheron (external and internal) allow us to create industrial clusters, sustainable both inside and outside, complementing each other and representing self-sufficient units. At the same time, these clusters are "open" and have sustainable linkages with surrounding areas. The functional enrichment of these clusters depends on the proposed functions (industry, housing, mixed-use space, etc.). Despite the single approach, this would offer the possibility of more diverse

development of selected industrial areas. But all clusters must be economically, environmentally and socially viable.

Conclusion

Returning to the issue of the development concept of the old industrial zones in Absheron, it should be noted that these problems are connected, first of all, with the change of the socio-political system and with the collapse in the economic development of the country. In the main industrial centers of Absheron (Baku, Sumgait), of the oldest and largest industrial hub of Azerbaijan (Absheron) production facilities did not functioned for a long time, and therefore, they are subjected to functional and moral depreciation, their technological cycles are outdated. The few operating enterprises are mostly unprofitable. Such issues have created significant challenges for the development of these cities and the integration of their large industrial zones into urban life. The problem is growing due to a huge shortage of land in Absheron, as well as the location of large industrial areas in the center of Baku and Sumgait, which could not be used now.

One of the main goals of this study was to determine a development concept of depressed industrial areas in Absheron. Based on the analysis of international experience and the structural-morphological analysis of industrial areas of Absheron it was demonstrated how to define the phasing of rehabilitation on these areas: area planning, focused on identifying current urban challenges at the macro level; harmonization with GBRDP and SRMNEA; choice of methods for renovation and rehabilitation. As a result of analysis of industrial zones in Absheron these areas were classified according to their investment appeal. This classification allowed us to show the development ways for selected categories of industrial zones.

The study also puts forward the basic principles of industrial facilities renovation, which are used in the development concept of the basic rehabilitation models of industrial zones in Absheron. The methodological framework of development concept of industrial areas in Absheron worked out by the author was given in the work. Thus, the study formulated the general concept of industrial zones rehabilitation in Absheron which includes creation of environmentally sustainable and people-centered, economically self-sufficient and active in innovative urban spaces. The concept is based on the construction of clusters, which are multifunctional self-sufficient sustainable structural unit.

Within the overall development strategy of Absheron industrial zones, the concept allows us to make different approach to rehabilitation of these areas, which can differ by location, investment appeal, urban planning, historical, economic, technical, socio-cultural, environmental and other characteristics. The article demonstrated how 4 various rehabilitation models of industrial zones are proposed for four different situations: "fragmentary" model, "linear-nodular" model, "complex" model, "evolutionary-revival" model.

I believe that such differentiated approach to various situations in Absheron, alongside with creation of environmentally sustainable, socially-oriented and economically self-sufficient, innovative and active urban

spaces, will also preserve the "spirit of the place", provide architectural diversity and careful integration of the rehabilitated area into the urban structure, as well as a high life quality that meets societal demands.

Bearing in mind the relevance of the study, as well as gaps in knowledge of the industrial zones rehabilitation in Absheron, I think that the proposed method will contribute to development of renovation and rehabilitation projects on industrial areas of Absheron. This study is an important stage in determining the principles of rehabilitation and redevelopment of depressed industrial areas in Azerbaijan and a necessary step in further study of urban systems. Further investigations will have to be carried out, in particular to expand the study area (for example, to include the other cities of Azerbaijan)

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